

1 **Genes encoded by the Mboat and GDF family function in aging in humans.**

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8 Citations

9 1. Valentine, W.J., Tokuoka, S.M., Hashidate-Yoshida, T., Yanagida, K., Suzuki, T., Inagaki, N.F.,
10 Motohashi, N., Nakano, K., Okamura, T., Kita, Y. and Shindou, H., 2025. MBOAT2 limits the amounts of
11 PUFA in phosphatidylcholine of neonatal and dystrophic skeletal muscle and promotes muscle
12 regeneration. bioRxiv, pp.2025-11.

13 2. Alharthi, J., Bayoumi, A., Thabet, K., Pan, Z., Gloss, B.S., Latchoumanin, O., Lundberg, M.,
14 Twine, N.A., McLeod, D., Alenizi, S. and Adams, L.A., 2022. A metabolic associated fatty liver disease risk
15 variant in MBOAT7 regulates toll like receptor induced outcomes. Nature Communications, 13(1), p.7430.

16 3. Mastrobattista, E., Lenze, E.J., Reynolds, C.F., Mulsant, B.H., Wetherell, J., Wu, G.F., Blumberger,
17 D.M., Karp, J.F., Butters, M.A., Mendes-Silva, A.P. and Vieira, E.L., 2023. Late-life depression is
18 associated with increased levels of GDF-15, a pro-aging mitokine. The American Journal of Geriatric
19 Psychiatry, 31(1), pp.1-9.

20 4. Torrens-Mas, M., Navas-Enamorado, C., Galmes-Panades, A., Masmiquel, L., Sanchez-Polo, A.,
21 Capo, X. and Gonzalez-Freire, M., 2025. GDF-15 as a proxy for epigenetic aging: associations with
22 biological age markers, and physical function. Biogerontology, 26(1), p.22.